

MECHANISM OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL OXIDATION OF AMMONIA. PART I. FORMATION OF INTERMEDIATE PRODUCTS.

BY W. V. SUNDARA RAO, P. V. KRISHNAMURTI AND G. GOPALA RAO.

The microbiological oxidation of ammonia to nitrite has been studied with particular reference to the formation of any possible intermediate products. Nitrite forming bacteria isolated from soils obtained from different parts of India have been used in the present investigation. Hydroxylamine and hyponitrite expected from theoretical considerations could not be detected in any of the numerous cultures examined by the known qualitative tests, some of which are very sensitive.

It has been known for a long time that ammonium salts, when added to the soil undergo oxidation to nitrite and nitrate. This transformation of ammonia to nitrate is commonly known as nitrification. It was Pasteur (*Compt. rend.*, 1862, 54, 265), who first suggested that the oxidation of ammonia is accomplished by micro-organisms. This was actually proved to be the case by two French Chemists, Schlosing and Muntz (*compt. rend.*, 1877, 84, 401; 88, 1018). They found that if a solution of ammonia was allowed to percolate through soil, which was well aerated at regular intervals, the ammonia was oxidised to nitrate. If the soil was heated to 100° or treated with antiseptics like chloroform it lost its capacity for oxidising ammonia. Warington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1878, 93, 44) further confirmed the biological nature of nitrification not only in soil but also in ammoniacal solutions seeded with soil. After many investigators have vainly endeavoured to isolate the organisms in pure culture, the Russian bacteriologist Winogradsky succeeded in obtaining a pure culture using silicic acid gel as the solid medium.

The researches of Winogradsky established that nitrification is really due to the joint action of two organisms: The nitrosomonas and nitrosococcus oxidise ammonia to nitrite; and nitrobacter oxidises nitrite to nitrate. The organisms are highly specific in character, the ammonia-oxidising bacteria have no action on nitrite, and the nitrite-oxidising organisms are without influence on ammonia. Since the pioneering work of Winogradsky much work has been done on the characteristics of these organisms by numerous investigators, notably Omeliansky (*Centl. Bakt.*, 1899, 2, 537), Meyerhof (*Fflugers. Arch. Ges. Physiol.*, 1916, 164, 353; 165, 229; 166, 240), Bonazzi (*J. Bact.*, 1923, 8, 343), Boljes (*Archiv Mikrobiol.*, 1935, 6, 79), Gopala Rao and Pandalai (*ibid.*, 1936, 7, 32).

Very little is known about the chemical course of oxidation. Mumford (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36; *cf.* Fowler, "Biochemistry of Nitrogen Conservation," 1934, p. 99) investigated the intermediate products formed in the nitrification of ammonium salts. He carried the experiments in filters inoculated from actively nitrifying sewage filters. The compounds identified were hydroxylamine salts and salts of hyponitrous and nitrous acids. As he used only a mixed culture from a sewage, it cannot be concluded from these results that hydroxylamine and hyponitrous acid will be formed in the normal course of oxidation of ammonia by the organism *nitrosomonas*. Beesley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 114) examined the rate of nitrification of urea, uric acid, asparagine, glycine, methylamine, acetamide, ammonium oxalate, and ammonium sulphate. He employed dilute solutions of the various compounds in the presence of suitable mineral nutrients and inoculated them with a mixed culture from a sewage filter. He inferred that possibly hydroxylamine and hyponitrous acids are formed as intermediate products. His experiments appear to be inconclusive, as he used a mixed culture containing many different types of organisms—this is evident from the fact that he obtained nitrification of complex nitrogenous compounds like asparagine, urea, etc., though *nitrosomonas* in pure culture is without action on such compounds. Maze (*compt. rend.*, 1921, 172, 173) thought that hydroxylamine is an intermediate stage in the oxidation of ammonia to nitrite. Kluyver and Donker (*Chem. Zelle. Gewebe*, 1926, 13, 134) tacitly assume the possible formation of hydroxylamine and hyponitrous acid. Corbet (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1575; 1935, 29, 1086) stated that he could identify hydroxylamine on occasions and hyponitrous acid frequently in nitrifying cultures. He has also estimated the amount of the hyponitrite formed. Nelson (*Centl. Bakt.*, 1931, ii, 83, 280) reported his failure to detect any hydroxylamine. Gopal Rao and Pandalai (*loc. cit.*) examined a very large number of nitrifying cultures at different stages and failed to detect hydroxylamine.

From the theoretical standpoint, the question of the formation of intermediate products is an important one. The Warburg theory of biological oxidations assumes activation of molecular oxygen by the "atmungsferment" present on the cell surface: then follows the oxidation of the substrate molecule by the activated oxygen. On the other hand, Wieland assumes that activation of the substrate molecule is more important than the activation of oxygen. He considers that the substrate molecule is activated in such a way that it can easily part with one or more molecules of hydrogen, which will subsequently combine with a suitable hydrogen acceptor like oxygen, methylene blue, etc. Thus according to Wieland, oxidation is

in essence a dehydrogenation—he has shown that many familiar cases of oxidation which are usually regarded to involve addition of oxygen are in reality cases of dehydrogenation, such oxidations being brought about in the absence of oxygen but in the presence of suitable hydrogen acceptors like methylene blue, nitrobenzene, quinone, etc. Progressive dehydrogenation may result in the formation of intermediate products. For instance, in the oxidation of ethyl alcohol to acetic acid by the *bacterium aceti* Wieland showed that acetaldehyde formation is an intermediate stage; and that the bacterium can oxidise acetaldehyde to acetic acid. This discovery lends considerable strength to Wieland's theory that most oxidations are dehydrogenations.

The following scheme represents the progressive dehydrogenation of ammonia in aqueous solution. It is well known that the nitrifying organisms bring about the oxidation in a medium that is definitely alkaline. The optimum p_{H} is about 8.4—a solution of ammonium sulphate is not acted upon as such; the presence of a mild base like calcium carbonate or magnesium carbonate is found necessary. It is clear that it is the ammonium hydroxide and not the ammonium ion that is involved.

or

Thus in the progressive dehydrogenation of ammonium hydroxide one expects hydroxylamine and hyponitrous acid as intermediaries. In view of the importance of the problem it was thought desirable to investigate this aspect carefully.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

For the culture of the nitrite forming organisms, the following medium was utilised.

Ammonium sulphate	2.0 g.
Sodium chloride	2.0
Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate	1.0
Magnesium sulphate	0.5
Ferrous sulphate	0.4
Sterile distilled water	1000 c.c.

Portions (100 c.c.) of this medium were poured into a sterile culture flasks of 500 c.c. capacity and sterilized. Sterile magnesium carbonate (1 g.) was then added to the solution. This was seeded with one gramme of garden soil. The flask was then plugged with sterile cotton and incubated at 30°. Nitrite at first developed slowly and then more rapidly during the later days of incubation. When nitrite was developed appreciably, as shown by the Griess-Ilosva reaction, a few drops of the culture solution were introduced by means of sterile platinum loop or sterile pipette into another sterile flask containing 100 c.c. of the fresh medium and 1 g. of magnesium carbonate. In this manner several transfers were made, each time before ammonia disappears completely. Thus by this method the nitrate former is eliminated and a fairly pure culture of the nitrite former is obtained; by this process of elective culture, other soil organisms are also eliminated.

Hydroxylamine.—The tests employed for the detection of hydroxylamine are those of (1) W. C. Ball, (2) Fischer (+ or 1 and 2—*vide* J. W. Mellor "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Vol. VIII, p. 295) and of J. Blom (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 121) as also those depending on the reduction of mercuric oxide and copper oxide. In many hundreds of cultures examined, hydroxylamine could not be detected. Our results are in agreement with those of Nelson (*loc. cit.*). The cultures were prepared from different soils, those from Waltair, Vizagapatam, Coimbatore, Raipur and Pusa. J. Blom has stated that the addition of acetone in small amounts (0.4 c.c. per litre) served the purpose of combining with the hydroxylamine and storing it. Even in this way we could not obtain the test.

Hyponitrites.—Corbet (*loc. cit.*) reported to have discovered a new and delicate test for hyponitrites: The reagent suggested is a mixture of equal volumes of a saturated solution of potassium periodate and a solution of resorcinol. This is said to give a cherry-red colour with a neutral or slightly acid solution of hyponitrite.

We have now carried out systematic work on the utility of this colour test. The reagent we employed was a mixture of equal volumes of an $M/5$ solution of resorcinol and saturated solution of potassium periodate. The mixture was prepared immediately before use, as it darkens on standing. We find that the nature and intensity of the colour depend on the H^+ ion concentration of the test solution. Reliable results are obtained at p_H 2 or p_H 3. To a buffer solution made up of 7 c.c. of $N/10$ -hydrochloric acid, and 3 c.c. of sodium citrate solution, 1 c.c. of the neutral test solution is added, followed by the addition of 2 c.c. of the resorcinol potassium periodate reagent. In the presence of hydroxylamine, hyponitrite and nitrite, a cherry-red colour is obtained in five to 15 minutes, the intensity of the colour depending on the amount of the substance present. At various H^+ ion concentrations, the above three substances behave similarly and we are to conclude that the test is not specific for hyponitrite. The test is sensitive down to 1 part of nitrite or hydroxylamine or hyponitrite in a million part of water.

In nitrifying cultures, nitrite is formed in increasing amounts and hence the above test will not be of any use to detect the formation of hyponitrite. The findings of Corbet that hyponitrite is detected by the above test are thus open to criticism. Corbet thought that the above test is specific for hyponitrite. This is not the case. Further work is in progress.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
ANDHRA UNIVERSITY, WALTAIR
AND
MEDICAL COLLEGE, VIZAGAPATAM.

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